

Reasons for consumer trust in health websites: An approach integrating Website-based factors and Personality-based factors.

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Abstract:

This research attempts to shed some light on the mechanism of the e-trust formation associated to a first phase and meeting between partners, based on the service quality delivered by the website and the personal characteristics of Internet users. An application on a health website showed that the website design, the quality and quantity of its content and the confidentiality politics are the main elements that impact positively the trust formation in health website. Moreover, it showed that disposition to trust has a positive and direct impact on the e-trust. In turn, the familiarity and the expertise of the Internet users play moderating roles.

Keywords: E-trust; Initial e-trust; E-service quality; Disposition to trust; Familiarity; Expertise; Health-based website.

Introduction

E-trust has been the subject of several researches in marketing and the researchers emphasized its important role in reducing uncertainties inherent to the virtuality of the Internet tool. However, the most of investigation fields were the online transactions and very few studies have investigated the trust formation in a non-commercial website. Furthermore, the most studies don't distinguish, in their conceptualization of trust, the specificities of the different trust typologies associated to each phase of the relationship between partners. Moreover, it should be noted that the elaboration of general models, that explain the e-trust formation and development, do not include the characteristics of each type of websites, the different users profiles and the influence of situational variables.

The limitation associated to the literature led us to wonder about the conformity of the designs of trusted websites to the needs, expectations and navigation behaviors of all user types. Thus and from these observations, we propose to elaborate a conceptual framework that explain the e-trust formation in a health website highlighting the role of web-based factors, notably the e-service quality, and the role played by personality-based factors. The integration of personality-based factors, such as disposition to trust, expertise and familiarity, constitute a considerable interest of the research because they are always present independently of situations and natures of trust relationships.

It is in this precise context that we propose to provide some answers to these questions: « What are the roles of website-based factors and personality-based factors in the formation of trust in health website? And what are the nature and the strength of these roles? ».

To answer these questions, we propose to achieve the following aims : (1) Identify the elements related to the quality of the health website that impact the e-trust formation, based on the quality of the service delivered by the website and to determine the impact of these elements on e-trust, (2) to determine the nature and strength of each personal characteristics in the formation of e-trust, (3) and finally, to study the impact of the trust in health website on behavioral intentions.

We propose to present, first, the conceptual framework of the research. Then, we will set out the methodology and the results of the empirical study. Finally, we will conclude with a discussion of the main results, the contributions, the limitations and future research.

Conceptual Background

1. E-trust

A literature review of the classical and electronic trust allowed us to conclude that it has been defined according to two main approaches. It was assimilated, by the followers of the psychological approach, to a psychological state of expectations or beliefs and a disposition to trust. According to the behavioral approach, trust is a willingness to be vulnerable and dependent. Furthermore, it was assimilated to a process that evolves over time and relation between partners (Ben Naoui and Zaiem, 2014).

This divergence of conceptualization has identified different types of trust associated to each phase of trust relationship. This is mainly:

- **Calculated-based trust:** It originates from the theory of economic transaction costs (Williamson, 1993). It's assimilated to an economic result of a comparison between benefits related to the creation of

the relation and the losses related to the maintenance or the breakdown of this relation (Ben Naoui, 2014).

- **Knowledge-based trust:** It serves to distinguish those who are trustworthy, mistrustful and unknown (Lewis and Weigert, 1985). The followers of this approach confirm that trust develops gradually through « social interactions » (Lewiki and Bunker, 1995; Shapiro et al., 1992) and « cumulative knowledges» between partners (Miller and Rempel, 2004).

- **Cognitive-based trust** refers to the set of the achievement of the promised and expected aims and commitment (Ben Naoui, 2014). It assumes that trusting beliefs forms quickly because of the set of institutional structures, reputation, judgments, dispositions, the need to cooperate, etc. (McKnight et al., 1998; McKnight et al., 2002).

- **Affective-based trust** is characterized by a security feeling and the perceived reliability of the partner (Ben Naoui, 2014). It appears at an advanced stage in the relationship development.

- **Initial trust** refers to a first encounter and interaction between the two parties of the trust relationship. It is formed through individual dispositions to trust, institution-based trust and the different cognitive process (McKnight et al., 1998; 2002).

In perfect agreement with the approach which assimilate the concept of trust as a process, we propose to focus in a first encounter and interaction between the Internet users and the website that emanates from the field of initial trust according to McKnight and al. (1998; 2002), who explain the initial trust formation through individual dispositions to trust without having “credible information about, or affective bonds with, each other” (Bigley and Pearce, 1998 cited in McKnight et al., 2002). This is consistent with the assumptions of the cognitive-based trust approach. However, this trust may change over time and experience between partners, which joins the hypothesis made by knowledge-based trust approach (Ben Naoui, 2014).

2. The website quality

To assess the websites quality, Internet users take into account the quality of service delivered by these websites. They assess, more specifically, their functional aspects, the quality of their content and finally the security policies and tools implemented to ensure the interactivity with users and the personalization of the offer.

The website functional quality refers to the quality of all elements related to the aesthetic, visual and sound appearance, as well as the set of the technical elements that facilitate the navigation on the site, the information search and the interaction with the site.

The content quality, as for it, refers to the richness, the variety, the clarity, the currency, the simplicity, the credibility and the relevance of information provided by the website. The politics of the security and the preservation of personal data exchanged during an online browsing experience are important factors taken into account by the Internet users in the evaluations of websites. Moreover, the literature has emphasized their influence in reducing risks inherent to online transactions with the works of Yang and Jun (2002); Bressolles (2002); Santos (2003); Zarrai and Gharbi (2007); Kassim and Ismail (2009); Ben Naoui and Zaiem (2014); etc.

In the case of non-commercial website, the example of informative websites, Bressolles and Nantel (2007) have identified five elements taken into account in the evaluations of e-services quality. It is the quality and quantity of information, the ease of use, the design, the security politics, the interactivity and the personalization.

The study of e-service quality as a major antecedent of e-trust has been the subject of several marketing researches, especially in works of Zha et al. (2006); Zarrai and Gharbi (2007); Kassim and Ismail (2009); Ghane and al. (2011); Ben Naoui and Zaiem (2014). Their empirical results have shown a positive and direct effect of the e-service quality on e-trust. Based on these empirical evidences, we propose to state the first hypothesis: « the e-service quality has a positive and significant impact on the e-trust formation».

3. Personality-based factors

3.1. Disposition to trust

Disposition to trust was the subject of several researches in different disciplines, but it finds its theoretical foundations in the psychological approach with the works of Rotter (1967, cited in Ben Naoui, 2014). In general, it has been defined according to two main approaches. The first approach assimilates it to a trait of personality, the examples of Sitkin and Pablo (1992); Kim and Tadisina (2007) researches. The second one defines it as a personal tendency and predisposition. McKnight and Chervany (2002), for example, have defined it as “a sustained tendency to be voluntary dependent on others whatever the situations and people involved in the exchange relationship”. In the same vein, McKnight et al. (1998) distinguish between the following two facets of disposition to trust:

- The faith in humanity which refers to the beliefs of the partner trustworthiness.
- The trusting stance refers to the beliefs of the trustworthiness and the reliability of others until proven otherwise (Ben Naoui, 2014).

The important role of the disposition to trust in the e-trust formation has been highlighted in several researches in e-commerce. Indeed, some researchers have shown that it plays a direct effect on e-trust (McKnight et al., 2002; McKnight and Chervany, 2002; Koufaris and Hampton-Sosa, 2002; Kim and Tadisina, 2007; Thompson and Jing, 2007; Kantsperger and Kunz, 2010; Ben Naoui and Zaiem, 2014). Others have shown that it plays a moderating role in the relationship between e-trust and its antecedents (Lee and Turban, 2001; Chen and Barnes, 2007; Zarrai and Gharbi, 2007).

It should be reminded that the focus of our research is the concept of initial e-trust based on the conceptualization of McKnight et al. (1998; 2002) which state that the effect of disposition to trust is significant when a person doesn't have enough information about his partner beforehand. Consequently, it is considered as an antecedent of the e-trust formation.

Thus, the second hypothesis is the following: « H2: disposition to trust has a positive and significant impact on the e-trust formation».

3.2. Familiarity and expertise

The familiarity is defined by Alba and Hutchinson (1987) as «the number of experiences related to the product and accumulated by the consumers». It's associated to the set of interactions between the consumer and the product, or between the activity and the information related to the product (Gharbi, 1998). In addition, the expertise refers to the person abilities to handle the product, to realize activities and to treat information related to it (Gharbi, 1998).

We note that in this present research, the familiarity with Internet is associated with the number of experience and interaction with the Internet tool. The Internet user's expertise is considered as his ability to perform tasks related to the online search information.

The e-trust literature demonstrate the important roles of the familiarity and the expertise in explaining the internet user's behavior and in the e-trust formation (for examples Gefen, 2000; Walczuch, Seelen and Lundgren, 2001; Bhattacharjee, 2002; Yoon, 2002; Corbitt et al., 2003; Gefen and Straub, 2004; Chouk and Perrien, 2004, 2005; Bart et al., 2005; Chen, 2006; Bressolles, 2006). However, some researchers opt for a direct effect of the familiarity and the expertise on the e-trust formation (Gefen, 2000; Bart et al., 2005), others have shown that the level of the user expertise and his familiarity with Internet play a moderating role in e-trust formation (Chouk and Perrien, 2004, 2005; Bressolles, 2006).

As Chouk and Perrien (2004, 2005); Bressolles (2006), we opt for the moderating role of these two characteristics. Thus, we propose to state the following hypothesis:

« H3: the higher the level of user familiarity with Internet tool, the greater the impact of e-service quality on the e-trust formation».

« H4: the higher the level of user expertise, the greater the impact of e-service quality on the e-trust formation».

4. Behavioral intentions

Previous e-commerce researches have noted that the e-trust boosts the development of positive attitudes toward websites (Ben Naoui and Zaiem, 2014) and influences behavioral intentions (Ben Naoui and Zaiem, 2014; Bart et al., 2005; Shankar and al., 2002; Yoon, 2002). Thus, users who are reassured, because of the establishment of a trustworthy climate, are willing to revisit the site, to reutilize it, to recommend it and to interact with it. This allows us to state the fourth hypothesis which stipulates: « H4: the e-trust has a significant and a positive impact on behavioral intentions».

Figure : Research model

Methodology

We used an online survey to validate the conceptual framework relative to the formation of trust in health websites and to test the research hypothesis. The aim was to reproduce real conditions of e-trust formation. The choice of the health website was done in three steps:

- The research stage: we started, first of all, selecting unknown websites because the objective is to study the first encounter between the Internet users and the website. This selection was made according to a certain number of criteria: (1) These websites should be interactive with sober colors, (2) The information provided by the websites should be signed by professionals or health experts and should allow the Internet users to interact with them in case of need, (3) These websites should allow the Internet user to customize the interface dedicated to him and should ensure the ease of information research and the security of personal information exchanged during the browsing experience.

- A group of experts: the selected websites in the first stage of research were been exposed to a group of experts. We asked them to verify the coherence between the research aims and the websites, the information credibility and, finally, the quality of technical and functional aspects.

The experts chose the site www.passeportsante.net.

- The website pretest: We also verified that the chosen website wasn't presenting navigation problems and that is aimed to both men and women of different ages.

After choosing the website, we drafted the questionnaire (see Appendix 1 for more details about

measurement scales) which was postulated in social networks. We explained to participants that they should, before answering to the questionnaire, devote the necessary time to visit the website and to explore all its pages, functionalities and sections. We have, also, asked them to do nothing during the browsing experience, not to interrupt the website visit, to participate only once, and, finally, not to participate to our online survey if they know already the website or they have had prior experience with the website. We finally collected 350 responses from Internet users with different socio-demographic characteristic.

Empirical study

To validate the measurement scales, we used, first, an exploratory factor analysis (EFA) and, second, a confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) through the structural equations method using the maximum likelihood method (ML). We note that this method of variables estimation requires the respect of the multi-normality of variables that have not been verified in our case. To correct this deviation, we used, first, the Bollen-stine bootstrap procedure (N=2000) in order to compare the difference between the Chi-square probability of the two models, with and without bootstrap. Then, and in order to make sure of the data stability, we examined the parameter values estimated by the ML method and those by the bootstrap method (N=250). Since the differences were less than 0.001, we interpreted the ML results.

Reliability and validity of e-trust measurement scale

The EFA results of the e-trust scale revealed a two-dimensional structure (benevolence-integrity and

competence). The Cronbach alpha of each dimension shows that the scale has a good internal consistency (Table 1). The results of a first CFA indicate that the measure model of e-trust doesn't present a good index fit. Indeed, the Chi-square/df exceeds the threshold set by Marsh and HOcevar (1985, cited in Akrou, 2010). Thus, and in order to improve the model, we made modifications related to the covariance of measurement errors by examining the values of the highest MI per change. These modifications improved the index fit and declined the value of the Chi-square/df (Chi-square/df=4.079 ; GFI=0.945 ; AGFI=0.897 ; RMR=0.027 ; RMSEA=0.094 ; NFI=0.951 ; CFI=0.962 ; TLI=0.943). We verified, also, the reliability at a confirmatory level and the validity of each e-trust dimension (see table1).

We noted that the superior order of e-trust is justified by several researchers, such as McKnight and al. (2002). Furthermore, the value of Target Coefficient Index TCI $([97,901/97,901] = 1)$ indicate that 100% of covariances between the first order factors can be explained by the second order factors. Consequently, the e-trust model structure converges to a superior order.

This structure presents a satisfactory index of fit (Chi-square/df =4.079 ; GFI = 0.945 ; AGFI = 0.897 ; RMR = 0.027 ; RMSEA = 0.094; NFI = 0.951 ; CFI = 0.962 ; TLI = 0.943). Finally, the verification of the reliability and the convergent and discriminant validity confirms the e-trust second-order factor.

Table 1: Reliability and validity of the e-trust measurement scale

	The reliability at an exploratory level	The reliability at a confirmatory level	The convergent validity (Fornell and Larker, 1981)	The discriminant validity (Fornell and Larker, 1981)	
	Cronbach's Alpha	Rh of Jreskog		Benevolence-Integrity	Competence
Benevolence-Integrity	0,903	0.886	0.612	0.612	—
Competence	0,888	0.872	0.633	0.286	0.633

Reliability and validity of the e-service quality measurement scale

Two principles components analysis (PCA) with a varimax rotation eliminated the two items IP1 and IP2 related to the dimension « interactivity and personalization » that presented very low qualities of representation. A third PCA was initiated without these items and the results showed satisfactory values of factors loading and qualities of representation. Cronbach's alpha, which indicate the reliability at an exploratory level, reveal a good internal consistency of the e-service quality measurement scale (see table 2).

Results of a first CFA showed that the squared multiple correlations (SMC) related to the items QI1 and D4 presented low values (SMC of QI1 = 0.303 and SMC of D4 = 0.378). So we decided to eliminate them and to initiate a second CFA. Results showed that the measurement model presents a good reliability at a confirmatory level with Rh of Jreskog's values included between 0.719 and 0.904. The measurement model of the e-service quality indicate a satisfactory index of fit (Chi-square/df =3.285 ; GFI = 0.931 ;

AGFI = 0.888 ; RMR = 0.036 ; RMSEA = 0.081; NFI = 0.926 ; CFI = 0.947 ; TLI = 0.927). Finally, we checked the convergent and discriminant validity by examining coefficients of the Rh of the convergent validity that are superior than the threshold 0.5 recommended by Roussel and al. (2002), and the values of the variance extracted that are superior than the squared correlations between dimensions.

The superior order of the e-service quality is justified by several researchers, notably Bressolles (2006). Besides, the comparison between the first-order model and the second-order model in terms of goodness of fit to the data by calculating the TCI reveal that 98.34% of the covariance between the first-order factors can be explained in terms of the second-order factors. Consequently, the structure of the e-service quality model converges to a superior order.

This structure presents a good goodness of fit (Chi-square/df =3.208 ; GFI = 0.930 ; AGFI = 0.890 ; RMR = 0.036 ; RMSEA = 0.080; NFI = 0.924 ; CFI = 0.946 ; TLI = 0.929). Finally, the verification of the reliability and the convergent and discriminant validity confirms the e-service quality second-order factor.

Table 2: Reliability and validity of the e-service quality measurement scale

	The reliability at an exploratory level	The reliability at a confirmatory level	The convergent validity (Fornell and Larker, 1981)	The discriminant validity (Fornell and Larker, 1981)			
	Cronbach's Alpha	Rh of Jreskog		1	2	3	4
1. Security/privacy	0,902	0.904	0.653	0.653			
2.Design	0,807	0.808	0.584	0.166	0.584		
3.Quality and quantity of information	0,695	0.719	0.566	0.210	0.193	0.566	
4.Ease of use	0,815	0.821	0.698	0.261	0.158	0.158	0.698

Reliability and validity of the disposition to trust measurement scale

The Cronbach's coefficients alpha relative to each dimension of disposition to trust reveal a good internal consistency of the scale at an exploratory level. The values of Rh of Jreskog of each dimension are superior than the threshold 0.6 recommended by Bagozzi and Yi (1988, cited in Akrouf, 2010). The measurement model of the disposition to trust indicate

globally a satisfactory goodness of fit (Chi-square/df =4.516 ; GFI=0.965 ; AGFI=0.965 ; RMR=0.040 ; RMSEA=0.100 ; NFI=0.977 ; CFI=0.982 ; TLI=0.966). Finally, we verified the convergent and discriminant validity by examining coefficients of the Rh of the convergent validity that are superior than the threshold 0.5 recommended by Roussel and al. (2002), and the values of the variance extracted that are superior than the squared correlations between dimensions.

Table 3: Reliability and validity of the disposition to trust measurement scale

	The reliability at an exploratory level	The reliability at a confirmatory level	The convergent validity (Fornell and Larker, 1981)	The discriminant validity (Fornell and Larker, 1981)	
	Cronbach's Alpha	Rh of Jreskog		Faith in humanity	Trusting stance
Faith in humanity	0,916	0.918	0.789	0.789	---
Trusting stance	0,872	0.880	0.712	0.495	0.712

We checked, later, if the two-dimensional structure of disposition to trust will move to a second-order confirmatory analysis. Thus, we examined the correlation between the two dimensions which is equal to 0.704 and the value of the TCI which is equal to 1. Consequently, the model structure converges to a superior order. In addition, this structure indicate a good goodness of fit (Chi-square/df =4.240 ; GFI=0.972 ; AGFI=0.917; RMR=0.037 ; RMSEA= 0.096; NFI=0.981 ; CFI=0.985 ; TLI=0.969). Finally, the verification of the reliability and the convergent and discriminant validity confirms the disposition to trust second-order factor.

Reliability and validity of the behavioral intentions measurement scale

The results of an EFA showed that the measurement scale of behavioral intentions have a good internal consistency (Cronbach's Alpha =0.872). The results of a CFA allowed us to eliminate an item with a SMC value less than 0.4. After purification, the scale has only three items, so it's considered as exactly identified. The reliability and the convergent validity of the scale are satisfactory with a value of Rh of Jreskog equal to 0.889 and a value of Rh of the convergent validity equal to 0.731.

Reliability and validity of the global measurement model

The global measurement model presents a good goodness of fit (Chi-square/df = 2.586 ; GFI = 0.855 ; AGFI = 0.816 ; RMR = 0.036 ; RMSEA = 0.040 ; NFI = 0.871 ; CFI = 0.916 ; TLI = 0.900). The reliability at

an exploratory level was checked with the Rhô of Jöreskog values that are superior than the threshold 0.6 recommended by Bagozzi and Yi (1988, cited in Akrouf, 2010) (see table 4). Furthermore, the values of Rhô of the convergent validity are superior than the

threshold 0.5 recommended by Rousset and al. (2002) (see table 4). And finally, the extracted variances values, which are superior to the squared correlations between the different dimensions, confirm the discriminant validity of our model (see table 5).

Table 4: Reliability and convergent validity of the variables of the global measurement model

	Rh of Jreskog P	Rh of the convergent validity ( _{vc})
Security/privacy	0,903	0,651
Design	0,807	0,584
Ease of use	0,820	0,695
Quality and quantity of information	0,653	0,582
Benevolence-integrity	0,889	0,618
Competence	0,874	0,636
Faith in humanity	0,918	0,789
Trusting stance	0,881	0,712
Behavioral intentions	0,891	0,734

Table 5: The discriminant validity of the measurement model

	Security/ privacy	Behavioral intentions	Ease of use	Quality and quantity of information	Benevolence- integrity	Competence	Faith in humanity	Trusting stance	Design
Security/ Privacy	0,651								
Behavioral intentions	0,230	0,734							
Ease of use	0,264	0,131	0,695						
Quality and Quantity of information	0,235	0,231	0,330	0,582					
Benevolence- integrity	0,313	0,161	0,142	0,211	0,618				
Competence	0,173	0,287	0,127	0,544	0,302	0,636			
Faith in Humanity	0,084	0,023	0,002	0,010	0,133	0,005	0,789		
Trusting stance	0,088	0,034	0,030	0,005	0,102	0,187	0,498	0,712	
Design	0,172	0,216	0,166	0,197	0,206	0,170	0,029	0,022	0,584

Causal model and hypothesis tests

The causal model of our research indicate a satisfactory goodness of fit (Chi-square/df = 2.771 ; GFI = 0.837 ; AGFI = 0.806 ; RMR = 0.083 ; RMSEA = 0.070 ; NFI = 0.852 ; CFI = 0.900 ; TLI = 0.888). The results of the causal links between e-trust,

disposition to trust, e-service quality and behavioral intentions are presented in the table 6. Hypothesis H.1, H.2 and H.5 are validated. Consequently, the e-service quality and the disposition to trust have positive and significant impacts on trust toward a health website. Besides, e-trust has a positive and significant impact on behavioral intentions.

Table 6: Relationship between e-trust, disposition to trust, e-service quality and behavioral intentions

Relations	CR	P	conclusions
E-trust ← E-service Quality	6.905	0.000*	H.1 is validated
E-trust ← Disposition to trust	2.472	0.013*	H.2 is validated
Behavioral Intentions ← E-trust	7.636	0.000*	H.5 is validated

Tests of moderating effects of familiarity and expertise

To test the moderating effects of familiarity with the Internet, we used a multi-group analysis with the modeling method by structural equations. We divided, first of all, the sample into two groups, the group of familiars with the Internet tool and the group of non familiars with the Internet tool. Then, we verified the existence of a significant difference of correlations between the two concepts (e-trust and e-service quality) and their measurement variables in the two groups. So, we conducted a CFA on the measurement items of the e-service quality and the e-trust knowing that the correlations were left without constraints.

Then, the same model was estimated by making equal the correlations between the two groups.

The test of Chi-square difference between the free model and the constrained model is significant (Chi-square=6.098 ; df=5 ; p=0.000). In order to determine the nature and the strength of the moderating role, we compared the standardized regression weights of each group (see table 7). Thus, the impact of the e-service quality on the e-trust is more important in the second group, the users who are familiars with the Internet. In other words, the higher the level of user familiarity with Internet tool, the greater the impact of e-service quality on the e-trust formation. This allows us to verify the third hypothesis.

Table 7: Results of the moderating effect of the familiarity with the Internet

	G1 : The non familiars			G2 : The familiars		
	Estimate	CR	P	Estimate	CR	P
E-trust ← E-Service Quality	0.661	5.669	0.000	0.726	5.158	0.000

We proceed in the same way to verify the moderating role of expertise. The test of Chi-square difference between the free model and the constrained model is significant (Chi-square=10.875 ; df=5 ; p=0.000). And by examining the standardized regression weights of each group (see table 8), we find

that the impact of the e-service quality on e-trust is much more important in the second group. In other words, the higher the level of user's expertise, the greater the impact of e-service quality on the e-trust formation. This allows us to verify the fourth hypothesis.

Table 8: Results of the moderating effect of the expertise

	G1 : The novices			G2 : The experts		
	Estimate	CR	P	Estimate	CR	P
E-trust ← E-Service Quality	0.452	4.888	0.000	0.885	4.750	0.000

Results and discussions

We tried throughout this research to provide answers to four main research aims: (1) to identify elements relative to the quality of a health-website that impact the e-trust formation based on the quality of the service delivered by the website, (2) to determine the impact of these elements on e-trust, (3) to determine the nature and the strength of each personal characteristic in the e-trust formation, (4) and finally, to study the impact of the trust toward health-website on behavioral intentions.

An empirical study was conducted on a health website. It revealed that the e-service quality has a positive impact on e-trust formation. These results are in perfect agreement with previous researches, notably with researches of Zha et al. (2006) ; Zarrai and Gharbi (2007) ; Kassim and Ismail (2009) ; Ghane and al.

(2011) ; Ben Naoui and Zaiem (2014). It revealed, furthermore, that the elements of e-service quality which determine the e-trust formation are the quality and quantity of information, the design and the security/privacy (See Appendix 2).

It seems, thereby, that Internet users, who are solicitous over their health, attach importance to the quality and quantity of information delivered on health websites. By the way, the literature has largely underlined the important role of this element in determining the e-trust, especially in works of Zarrai and Gharbi (2007). Similarly, the design of a health website is an eminent antecedent to the e-trust formation. This finding converges with those of Bressolles (2002). The politics of the security and the preservation of personal data exchanged during an online browsing experience determine, also, the e-trust

formation. This converges with results of Kassim and Ismail (2009).

The major interest of our research is the inclusion of personality-based factors in the e-trust formation, notably the disposition to trust, the familiarity and the expertise, that are always present regardless of situations and trust relationships between partners. Indeed, we showed that disposition to trust has a positive and significant impact on the e-trust formation. These results coincide with those of McKnight et al. (2002); McKnight and Chervany (2002); Koufaris and Hampton-Sosa (2002); Kim and Tadisina (2007); Thompson and Jing (2007); Kantsperger and Kunz (2010); Ben Naoui and Zaiem, (2014).

Results of the empirical study, that we conducted, attest of the moderating effects of the familiarity with the Internet and the expertise of the Internet users in the research of e-health information on the formation of trust toward a health website. These results are in agreement with those of Chouk and Perrien (2004; 2005); Bressolles (2006). They show, in addition, the significant and positive impact of e-trust on behavioral intentions. These results are similar to those of Bart et al. (2005); Ben Naoui and Zaiem (2014).

Contributions, limitations and future research

The main objective of our research was to propose a conceptual framework that explains the mechanism of initial e-trust formation in the case of health-based website. The fact to focus on the field of initial trust, which emanate from a first meeting and interaction between partners, is essentially justified by our belief that trust is a process that evolves over time and interactions between partners.

This framework allowed us to underline the important role of the quality of the service delivered by the website, the disposition to trust, the familiarity and the expertise in e-trust formation. Indeed, the e-service quality and disposition to trust are important determinants of trust in health website. In turn, the familiarity and expertise play moderating roles in e-trust formation.

Our research proposes some managerial recommendations to be taken into consideration in conceptions of health-based websites. Indeed, designers must pay particular attentions to two main elements, the quality of services delivered by websites and the diverse characteristics of Internet users. Thus, designers must, first of all, identify, examine and assimilate the different natures and profiles of Internet users, and to adapt, then, websites conceptions according to the different typologies already identified.

Consequently, designers of health websites must focus on the quality of information and the visual and aesthetic aspects of the website, so that they can appeal to all types of users, whether beginners or familiar with the Internet, experts or novices in the e-health information search. Thus, the care given to the design of health websites must take into account the quality of the website content, its ergonomics, its visual harmony and the sobriety of the colors used. The goal is to guarantee to internet users an experience rich of informations and visually attractive. However, the richness of information doesn't mean the length of unnecessary details. On the contrary, the content must be exhaustive, clear, precise, understandable and up-to-date, and accompanied by explanatory diagrams or videos with short duration.

Another element must be treated with precaution by health websites designers. It's the confidentiality of personal data exchanged during the browsing experience on the site. Indeed, users who care about their health are still reluctant and mistrustful because of possible misuse of informations shared with the site. This type of internet user can be reassured if he will feel in a situation of controlling the browsing experience in its integrality. Consequently, designers must provide the website with tools and devices allowing them to access to confidentiality politics and to modify or to delete personal data safely and without access restriction.

Our research presents some limits that can be exploited and improved in future researches. Indeed, the method of data collection has raised two main issues. The first is characterized by the difficulty of controlling the online experience and the second is relative to the nature of the sample which may affect the generalization of results. Similarly, limiting the field of investigation to one health website poses the problem of generalization of results. We would have had to expand the scope of investigation to other websites and compare the results in order to generalize them to all health websites.

Focus on an advanced stage of the trust relationship, taking into account the importance of past experiences and interactions, can be an interesting field of investigation. This allows us to examine the nature of causal relationships between personal characteristics and e-trust associated to each stage of the relationship.

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Appendix

Appendix 1: Measurement scale

E-Service quality	Bressolles and Nantel (2007)	5 dimensions, 16 items 5 likert-type scale
E-trust	McKnight and al. (2002)	3 dimensions, 11 items 5 likert-type scale
Disposition to trust	Teo and Liu (2002) Chen (2006)	2 dimensions, 6 items 5 likert-type scale
Familiarity Expertise	Bressolles (2006)	A limit of more or less than 2 years.

Appendix 2: Relationship between the dimensions of ESQ, and e-trust

Relations	Stand.reg.weight	Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P
E-trust <--- Qu/quan-infor	0.567	0.282	0.059	4.794	0.000
E-trust <--- Secu-Privacy	0.469	0.186	0.031	6.097	0.000
E-trust <--- Design	0.380	0.154	0.030	5.112	0.000
E-trust <--- Ease-use	0.094	0.038	0.026	1.425	0.154